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1. Front view of the portable, inclined-axis straw and forage chopper.

2. The chopper blades: four rotating blades angled 10° upward and a fixed counterblade.

was measured through an AC power meter and calibrated motor. Capacity was measured by weighing the chopped material output over time. Specific energy, a measure of energy efficiency, is the quotient of power and capacity. Fineness of chop was expressed as percent chopped materials with length of 25 mm or less (L25) and 50 mm or less (L50).

Power and capacity generally increased with speed and inversely with clearance. Speed had no significant effect on length of chop. For napier grass, the highest capacity and the least specific energy were obtained at 1500 rpm. At 2 mm clearance, 70.9% moisture content, and 1500 rpm, the power was 0.613 kW; capacity, 1.114 t/h; specific energy, 0.552 kW-h/t; L25, 30%; and L50, 94%.

For corn stalks at 2 mm clearance, the highest capacity and least specific energy were obtained at 1050 rpm, which was not significantly different from 1200 rpm. At 1050 rpm, the power was 2.302 kW; capacity, 1.148 t/h; specific energy, 2.016 kW-h/t; L25, 23%; and L50, 93%. Chop-

ping corn stalks required almost 4 times as much power as napier grass at the same clearance because of larger stalk cross-sections and more stiffness.

Chopping rice straw with 65.9% moisture yielded 27% higher capacity than that with 47.8% moisture, which indicates straw must be chopped as fresh as possible. At 65.9% moisture, the highest capacity was obtained at 1500 rpm at which the power was 1.026 kW;

Using rice hulls to fuel a portable gasifier-engine system

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We investigated using biowaste, such as rice hulls, as a farm energy source to power a portable gasifier and engine system.

The gasifier (25 cm diam), based on a design developed at the University of California at Davis, USA, was matched with a Chinese S-195 diesel engine rated at 8.8 kW/2000 rpm and with a compression ratio of 20:1. Fuel injection timing (1-1.5° crankshaft angle before top dead center) and range of air to gas ratio of 1.1:1.4 were slightly retarded to permit satisfactory dual-fueled engine operation. The raw gas from the gasifier was ventilated through a wet sieve plate scrubber, a packed bed, and a paper filter to remove tar, water, and particulates. A gas-air mixture device to produce a gas to air ratio of 1.0:1.5 was mounted upstream of the engine manifold for dual-fuel running.

The gasifier generated a nearly uniform flow of raw gas, corrected to normal conditions (N) of 760 mm Hg atmospheric pressure and 20°C temperature, of 17-18.4 Nm³/h with a lower heating value (LHV)

capacity, 0.744 t/h; specific energy, 1.475 kW-h/t, L25, 26%; and L50, 62%.

The power was 0.960 kW; capacity, 0.664 t/h; specific energy, 1.446 kW-h/t; L25, 96%; and L50, 100% for chopping sesbania at 1500 rpm.

Field tests showed that the blades became dull after continuous chopping of 8-10 t corn stalks. The 3.5-hp engine consumed 0.5 liter gasoline/t corn stalks chopped. ■

of 4.02 MJ/Nm³. The specific gas output was 2.39 Nm³/kg rice hulls; the gasifier's cold gas efficiency was 52.6%. The optimal specific gasification rate was between 185 and 195 kg/m² per h. One batch of rice hulls lasted for 1.5 h.

Characteristics of the dual-fueled engine, without major modification, follow the appropriate torque level of 0.65-0.70 of the rated torque level when on straight diesel (see table). The drop of the brake parameter was observed because of the much lower LHV of the gas and flame velocity. Pilot diesel fuel injection was 10.2% of the injection amount with diesel fuel alone. Thermal efficiency was 30.6%, which was slightly lower than when diesel fuel was used. We observed a change of <3% variance in engine speed due to the change of torque level between 0 and 25 N-m, a slight difference in the sound level between operational modes, and an increase in pilot injection of 6.9% at onset of detonation and knocking at output of 6.3 kW at 2000 rpm.

The system satisfactorily pumped water for a continuous 60 h. Diesel fuel consumption for this task could be reduced by 89.8% if rice hulls were used to produce gas to power a dual-fueled system. Total fuel cost for the dual-fueled mode was 5.9 times less than that of the diesel-fueled mode. ■

Engine performance and operational cost when run under diesel fuel and dual fuels (diesel and rice hull). CNRI, China.

Operational mode	Power (kW)	Brake thermal efficiency (%)	Specific fuel consumption		Total fuel cost ^a (US\$/kW-h)
			Diesel fuel (g/kW-h)	Rice hull (kg/kW-h)	
Diesel fuel	8.8	32.2	254.36	-	0.053
Dual fuel	5.6	30.6	25.97	1.125	0.009

^aDiesel fuel: US\$0.21/kg; rice hull: US\$0.0035/kg.